

Deliverable D12.1 Tools for ontology and metadata management, and metadata interoperability

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Change Log

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CHEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DOID	Human Disease Ontology
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GO	Gene Ontology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MP	Mammalian Phenotype Ontology
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NCIT	National Cancer Institute Thesaurus
PIDAR	Preclinical Image DATaset Repository
PRISM	PReclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata
SWO	Software Ontology
UBERON	Uber Anatomy Ontology
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
XNAT	eXtensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit

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Executive Summary

Image data is one of the fastest growing types of research data, characterized by rapid advances in imaging technologies and workflows of increasing complexity. This growth places significant pressure on the research community to establish and maintain consistent metadata standards — a task that is technically demanding and requires sustained policy coordination across institutions, platforms, and funding bodies. Metadata harmonisation is not a one-time achievement but an ongoing governance responsibility, and the absence of shared ontological frameworks remains one of the principal obstacles to cross-platform data interoperability.

One of the central aims of the foundingGIDE project is to address this challenge by harmonising image metadata across data repositories at a European and global scale and to provide open and easy-to-use tools for the preclinical imaging community to improve metadata annotation, storage and preclinical image dataset curation.

To this aim, several tools have been developed and provided to the community for metadata curating, for improving findability of open dataset in XNAT repositories and for linking repositories based on the XNAT platform for making datasets more findable and queryable.

1. Introduction

The preclinical imaging field currently faces major obstacles in terms of interoperability and data discoverability. Many preclinical imaging datasets are not easily accessible due to the lack of dedicated repositories, lack of standardized metadata descriptions and difficulties in dataset annotation and curation. As a result, a substantial portion of imaging data is not sufficiently compliant with the FAIR principles, particularly regarding interoperability and reusability.

Work Package 12 responds to these challenges by developing necessary tools for interoperable imaging data management that supports harmonization across the worldwide preclinical imaging community and contributes to the broader global effort to build an open, interoperable image data ecosystem.

WP12 focuses on developing and deploying tools that allow interoperability across preclinical image dataset platforms based on the XNAT platform (an open platform for managing medical image datasets) and to facilitate FAIRification of preclinical imaging datasets. Three complementary and integrated components have been developed:

1. a JSON-based metadata input mechanism for the XNAT Custom Forms module and a dedicated XNAT plugin for linking metadata to image datasets.
2. a Python-based workflow for the automated extraction of ontology ID codes from web-based ontology repositories for dataset curation.
3. a pipeline for interoperability across several XNAT instances.

2. Linking metadata to preclinical image dataset in the XNAT platform

2.1. JSON Metadata Input for XNAT Custom Forms

XNAT provides a Custom Forms module that allows project administrators to attach additional metadata fields to subjects, experiments, and scans beyond the default DICOM-derived fields. In the FoundingGIDE deployment, Custom Forms are used to capture PReclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata (PRISM) information (as described in **Deliverable 8.1**¹) that are not natively stored in XNAT.

In Task 12.1 a JSON schema file has been developed that defines the full PRISM metadata set in the format expected by the XNAT Custom Forms API. The schema includes field names, data types, allowed values for controlled vocabulary fields, and mapping to XNAT data levels (project, subject, experiment, scan). Imaging centre administrators can import this schema via the XNAT REST API endpoint `/xapi/customforms/projectform/{projectId}` to instantiate the PRISM form for their project.

During development, an issue was identified with the XNAT 1.9.x Custom Forms datatype dropdown, which failed to populate correctly due to a bug in the `/xapi/role/displays/createable` endpoint on certain XNAT builds. A client-side workaround was implemented by patching the `datatypeManager.js` file to query the `/REST/search/elements` endpoint instead; this patch is persisted via a Docker volume mount in the FoundingGIDE XNAT deployment.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20808335>

2.2. XNAT Metadata Plugin

To provide a richer graphical interface for metadata entry and to handle metadata that requires server-side processing (ontology validation, cross-field consistency checks), a dedicated XNAT plugin has been developed in Java following the XNAT plugin framework.

The plugin provides: a project-level metadata configuration panel allowing administrators to select which PRISM fields are active for their project; an experiment-level metadata form pre-populated from DICOM tags extracted at upload time, with editable fields for PRISM attributes not available in DICOM; and REST API endpoints under `/xapi/pidar/` for programmatic read and write access to PRISM metadata stored in the XNAT database.

The plugin JAR is deployed to the XNAT plugins directory (`/mnt/data/xnat/plugins/` in the FoundingGIDE Docker deployment). The current plugin version has been tested and validated against two XNAT 1.9.xx instances (`eubi-xnat.hpc4ai.unito.it`) and (`xnat.ibb.cnr.it`) and has been made freely available at https://github.com/cim-unito/Pidar_XNAT_metadata_UI, please check the [releases](#) on the right side of the page.

The plugin allows to store metadata information and to automatically show some metadata information, such as species, organ/tissue, disease model, modality and sample size from the JSON file at upload, with any requested manual entry (**Figure 1**).

The screenshot shows the user interface for a dataset named 'pde5_liver'. It features a 'Details' tab with the following information:

- ID:** pde5_liver
- Description:** Fat fraction and ADC maps quantification in pde5 deficient mouse model
- View Custom Field(s)** button

Below the details, there is a section for 'Metadata from PIDAR' with the following extracted information:

- Dataset ID:** 26
- Species:** Mice
- Organ/Tissue:** brain, adipose tissue
- Disease Model:** metabolic disease
- Imaging Modality:** MRI
- Sample Size:** 14

There is also a 'Link to PIDAR' button. On the right side, an 'Actions' menu contains 'Download XML' and 'Download Images' options.

Figure 1. Plugin UI on XNAT instances showing the metadata stored in the json file

3. Automated extraction of ontologies for preclinical image dataset curation

In Tasks 12.2 a Python-based tool was developed using Flet to support the mapping of specific metadata (as developed in **Deliverable 8.1**) extracted from a predefined Microsoft Excel template to ontology terms retrieved via the BioPortal search API. The system implements a three-step workflow, guided by a dedicated graphical user interface that assists the user throughout the entire process and facilitates interaction with the tool. First, a structured Excel file containing metadata values is uploaded into the application. Second, each metadata value is automatically queried against BioPortal (<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>) to retrieve candidate ontology terms. Finally, the

selected ontology codes and their associated synonyms are exported to output files. The tool has been made publicly available at https://github.com/foundingGIDE/search_ontologies and https://bio.tools/search_ontologies.

3.1. Metadata Template and Ontology Mapping

The application reads metadata values from a structured Excel file provided by the user who contributes a dataset to the PIDAR repository. Specifically, it extracts values from a predefined set of metadata fields, including imaging modality, disease model, species, strain, immune status, genotype, gene information, drugs, and routes of administration.

A JSON configuration file defines the mapping between each metadata domain and the ontologies (as defined in **Deliverable 4.1**) to be queried (**Figure 2**). For example, disease-related terms are mapped to DOID, drug-related terms to CHEBI, anatomical terms to UBERON, imaging terms to NCIT, phenotypic terms to MP, analysis-related terms to SWO, strain information to EFO, and gene-related terms to GO.

Figure 2. Schema linking metadata fields to ontologies.

3.2. Ontology Term Extraction and User Validation

Ontology term retrieval was implemented using the BioPortal Search API (ref: <https://data.bioontology.org/documentation>). Ontology terms were retrieved through the BioPortal /search endpoint by submitting each metadata term as the query string (q) and constraining the search to the domain-specific ontology using the ontologies parameter.

The application provides a graphical user interface developed with Flet. After loading the Excel metadata template, the interface displays the metadata value and the target ontologies. Once the ontology search is initiated, the application retrieves the most relevant candidate ontology terms returned by BioPortal and presents them to the user. For each candidate term, the ontology code, URI, and available synonyms are displayed.

Rather than automatically assigning a single ontology term, the system generates a list of candidate matches for each metadata value. This approach reduces the effort required to manually search for ontology terms while maintaining expert supervision. Users can examine the retrieved candidates and select the most appropriate ontology term for each metadata value via the graphical interface.

3.3. Workflow Outputs

The implementation of the proposed workflow has demonstrated several practical advantages for metadata standardization in preclinical imaging datasets. The tool provides a list of candidate ontology terms for each metadata value, together with their synonyms, allowing users to evaluate multiple options and select the ontology code that is most appropriate for the dataset context (**Figure 3**). This retrieval strategy preserves expert control during the final selection phase. Furthermore, combining automatic ontology term retrieval with expert validation improves metadata mapping efficiency by reducing the manual effort required for ontology searches and code assignment.

After the validation phase, the results can be exported in CSV or Excel format. Two output files are generated. The first, *Ontology Codes*, contains one row per dataset, with the selected ontology codes grouped according to their corresponding metadata fields. The second, *Ontology Synonyms*, is a two-column table (*Ontology Code* and *Synonyms*) that lists the synonyms associated with the selected ontology terms (**Figure 4**).

Code	Domain	Value	Ontology	Synonyms	IRI	
B21	imaging modality	MRI	NCIT: C115501	Magnetic Resonance Imaging Study File, Magnetic Resonance		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
B21	imaging modality	MRI	NCIT: C16809	Magnetic Resonance, nuclear magnetic resonance imaging.		<input type="checkbox"/>
B21	imaging modality	MRI	NCIT: C154036	Maori Language, MRI, Maori		<input type="checkbox"/>
B22	imaging submodality	T2W	NCIT: C180729	T2-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging, T2-		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
B22	imaging submodality	DCE	NCIT: C62665	Dynamic Contrast-Enhanced Magnetic Resonance Imaging.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

List of candidate ontology terms for the metadata term “MRI”.

Figure 3. List of candidate ontology terms: for each metadata term, the tool provides a list of candidate ontology terms. For the metadata term MRI, multiple ontology codes and their corresponding synonyms are displayed, allowing the user to select the appropriate ontology code.

Ontology codes

DatasetId	NcitImagingModality	NcitImagingSubmodality	UberonImagingCoverage	DoIdDiseaseModel	UberonOrganOrTissue	SwoStatisticalMethods	NcitSpecies	EfoStrain
id 00010	NCIT:C115501	NCIT:C180729;NCIT:C62665	UBERON:0000955	DOID:162	UBERON:0000955	SWO:1100011	NCIT:C14363	EFO:0007736;EFO:0000602

Ontology synonyms

OntologyCode	Synonyms
NCIT:C115501	Magnetic Resonance Imaging Study File;Magnetic Resonance Imaging Subcategory;MRI
NCIT:C180729	T2-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging;T2-Weighted MRI;T2W MRI
NCIT:C62665	Dynamic Contrast-Enhanced Magnetic Resonance Imaging;DYNAMIC CONTRAST ENHANCED MRI;DCE;DCE MRI;DCE-MRI
UBERON:0000955	suprasegmental levels of nervous system;suprasegmental structures;synganglion;encephalon;the brain
DOID:162	primary cancer;malignant tumor;malignant neoplasm
SWO:1100011	ANNOVA
NCIT:C14363	NSF/N Mice
EFO:0007736	Non-obese Diabetic;NOD
EFO:0000602	BALB/c;BALB;c

Figure 4. The export process creates two files. Ontology codes: one row per dataset, with ontology codes grouped by metadata. Ontology synonyms: a two-column list of OntologyCode and Synonyms for selections.

4. Interoperability across several XNAT Instances

Task 12.3 targets interoperability across multiple XNAT instances, enabling researchers to discover and access open preclinical imaging datasets stored at different XNAT instances from a single interface, without needing to find or query into each XNAT instance individually.

4.1. Original Design and Technology Reassessment

The initial design for Task 12.3 envisaged a federated query layer built on top of the XNAT REST API and a central metadata aggregation service, exposed via a GraphQL endpoint and accessed through a Python-based Jupyter Notebook interface using [ipywidgets](#). In this design, users would select participating XNAT nodes, apply filters over PRISM metadata fields (species, modality, disease model, imaging centre), and retrieve results as a pandas DataFrame exportable to CSV or DATS JSON.

During implementation, this approach was reassessed for two reasons. First, a standalone Python/Jupyter solution would require users to manage a separate execution environment, creating an adoption barrier for non-technical researchers. Second, the FoundingGIDE technical stack is already built on ASP.NET Core 8, and consolidating all functionality within the PIDAR web application offers a significantly simpler deployment and maintenance path. Accordingly, the interoperability layer was redesigned and implemented directly within PIDAR as a dedicated XNAT page, reusing the existing infrastructure, authentication model, and UI framework.

4.2. Implementation: PIDAR XNAT Public Projects Page

The interoperability feature is implemented as a dedicated page within the PIDAR web application (pidar.hpc4ai.unito.it/Home/Xnat). The page aggregates and displays all public projects from the XNAT instances registered in the FoundingGIDE infrastructure, presenting them in a unified interface alongside an interactive geographic map that shows the location of each contributing node.

The aggregation logic is implemented as a server-side ASP.NET Core service that queries each registered XNAT instance via the standard XNAT REST API endpoint `/data/projects`, retrieving only projects marked as publicly accessible. For each project, the service assembles a summary card containing the dataset ID, species, organ/tissue, disease model, imaging modality, and sample size — fields that map directly to PRISM metadata categories defined in D8.1. Each card provides an ‘Open in XNAT’ link that redirects the user to the corresponding project on the originating XNAT instance.

Within the lifespan of the project, four XNAT instances have been registered and shown on the map: the EuroBioImaging/CNR-IBB node in Turin, The University of Milano-Bicocca in Milan, the CNR-IBB node in Naples, and the Australian Imaging Service (AIS) node at the University of Sydney from the Australian National Imaging Facility (NIF). These collectively expose open preclinical imaging datasets covering MRI, optical imaging, and PET/CT datasets (**Figure 5**).

Public preclinical projects on XNAT instances

Figure 5. Interactive map on the PIDAR XNAT page showing the geographic distribution of connected XNAT nodes. Four nodes are currently registered: three in Italy (EuroBioImaging/CNR-IBB in Turin, University of Milano-Bicocca in Milan and CNR-IBB Naples) and one in Australia (AIS, University of Sydney). Map rendered using the Leaflet.js library with OpenStreetMap/CARTO tiles.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable describes the suite of tools developed in WP12 of the FoundingGIDE project to support metadata storage, ontology annotation, and cross-node interoperability for preclinical imaging datasets. Three main components have been delivered: a JSON schema and XNAT plugin for PRISM metadata storage within XNAT, a Python-based ontology term extraction tool integrated with PIDAR and XNAT, and a web-based UI that allows interoperability and discoverability across multiple XNAT instances.

Together these tools make preclinical imaging datasets findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable in line with the FAIR principles.